

OSTEOINDUCTION USING AUTOLOGOUS BONE MARROW IN DIFFICULT ORTHOPAEDIC PROBLEMS

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Abstract

Objectives

The role of bone marrow injection in treatment of non-united long bones fractures.

Background:

There are many methods for the osteoinduction. Most of these methods are very expensive and sometimes these are also very extensive The most common nature for new bone formation is our own bone marrow. In 1869 first time it was described. There are many studies available showing new bone formation with bone marrow or its components. we are using bone marrow as a whole to treat deferment orthopedic condition by using its ability of new bone formation.

Methods:

We conducted this study in Mayo hospital Lahore from 1-4-18 to 1-10-18. All patients of either age were include in the study. The only criteria were nonunion. There was no age limit. All patient with internal fixation or with external fixation were included in the study.

Under sterile precautions all patients were treated in main operation theater. Iliac crest was used for bone marrow aspiration. Under image intensifier about 30 ml bone marrow was aspirated with a sternal puncture needle and injected at fracture sites. Union was assessed by x-rays. X-ray was done at every moth till six months. 2 to 4 injections may be given with the interval of 4 to 6 weeks.

Results

Total patients were 20. Union was achieved in 16 (80%) patients and there was no union in four (20%) patients. one patient was given 3 injections and other 3 got 4 injections. No complication was noted.

Conclusion:

Bone marrow injection is very simple, cheep and reliable method and can be used for osteo induction in deferent orthopedic conditions if the fixation is stable.

Introduction

Nonunion are of two types ,1, hypertrophic and 2, atrophic. There is attempt of bone union with

excessive callus formation but the fractures are not stable in hypertrophic nonunion 17 . Only stable Fixation and compression of bone fragments

resulted in union. In atrophic nonunion there is no callus Or paucity of callus formation. The bone ends are sclerosis and a gap is visible between bone ends on x-ray. The fracture fixations is usually stable. These kinds of nonunion need biological solution d.28. There are many kind of biological solutions are available It may be, bone grafts It can be either natural or synthetic bone growth factors. Now a days platelets rich plasma with its platelet derived and other growth factors are getting popularity There are also very good results of stem cells and demineralized bone matrix etc.29 Bone marrow contains a population of rare progenitor cells capable of differentiating into osteoblasts, chondrocytes, adipocytes, and muscle cells [1].

The osteogenic capabilities of bone marrow prompted surgeons to begin using it as a bone graft material.

Hernigou et al. 20 Patients with tibia nonunion were treated with bone marrow injection. Union was reported in all cases [2].

It was reported that some cell originates from the bone marrow and these cells take part in hard callus [3].

Stem cells from bone marrow converts in to both hematopoietic and non hematopoietic stem cells or marrow stromal cells. All blood component ,bone and cartilage cells are developed from these progenitor cells. [4].

The nonunion and acutue defect in fresh trauma are best treated by autograft from iliac crest. The procedure is pain full and increased the morbidity. Bone marrow injection is the best solution [5].

The most modern trend is to use of cell separator to separate osteo progenitor cells .These cells are cultured more and more osteoprogenitor cells are created. These and mixing bone marrow with Coralline Hydroxyapatite, Bioglass or tricalcium phosphate which acts as a scaffold for the bone formation and these are some of the methods practiced21.

In 1869 Goujon 22 described first time the bone induction quality of bone marrow in rabbit

. McGaw and Habin were first to described the osteogenic quality of bone marrow23.

Herzog in 1951 introduced the concept of percutaneous treatment. 4.

Connolly and Shindell were, the first to performed the per cutaneous bone marrow injection for union ininfected non union of tibia 24. Both stromal and endosteal cells are responsible for bone induction . Two types of cells are responsible . One to produce bone (IOPC) and second is to produce bone (DOPC). The former (IOPC) exists in all connective tissue and the latter (DOPC) is found only in the marrow2 5.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

Patients with either gender
No age limit
4 months after fractures
Fractures with nonunion

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Delayed union
Intra articular nonunion
Tumor nonunion
Pathological nonunion
Spinal fractures nonunion
Nonunion with loose implants
Infected donor site
Nonunion in hands and foot bones

Patients and methods

Total patients were 20. Male were 16(80%) and female were 4(29%). All patients were treated at Mayo hospital Lahore from 1-6-18 to 1-3-19. Nonunion was on rightsized in 14 (70%) patients and nonunion was on left side in 6 (30%) patients. The range of the age was from 10 years to 63 years .36.5 years was mean age of the treating patients The original fractures was open in 10(50%) patients. 5(25%) patients had close fractures and 5(25%) patients had closed fractures but got infected after surgeries.

At the time of bone marrow injections their fractures were managing in following methods

Pop cast were applied in 4(20%) cast, plates and screws were in 4(20%) patients, intramedullary locking nails were in 7(35%) patients, Ilizarov external fixators was in 3(15%) patients, uniplanar external fixator were in 1(5%) patient, and elastic nail was in 1(5%)0patient. Infected nonunion was suspected in 4 (20%) patients although there was not frank pus present at the wound. Sinus marks

were presents in 2 of infected patients. All lab investigations were normal. had a past history of presence of infection in the site of nonunion.

.We used C-arm in all our cases .Under aseptic conditions nonunion site was identified .A wide bore needle was inserted et nonunion site .Trimming and refreshing of the fracture edges were with these needles .This needle was kept in nonunion site . Then bone marrow was done with another needle from anterior superior iliac spine. About 30 ml bone marrow was at least aspirated. This aspirated marrow was injected into the injection needles already inserted into the nonunion site.

Postoperatively all patients were advised non weight bearing in case of nonunion at lower limb . and immobilization with pop cast in upper limb nonunion. In first month patients were examined after 15 days then after one month's till final examination after 6 months. clinical and radiological assessment

Were done every month.

The statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 16.0 was considered to be statistically significant.

Results

Bone marrow injection was done in all 20 patients .2 injections was given in 2(10%) patients and union was occurred in these patients. 3 injections were given in 11 (55%) patients. Union was occurred in 10 patients and one patient was not healed .4 injections were given in 7(35%)patients and union occurred in all patients 4 patients and 3 patients were not healed

6(30%) patients were smokers and from these 6 patients 3(50%)patients were achieved union In.

In total of 20 patients 6(30%) patients had nonunion at femurs. 4(66.66%) patients of then got union after bone marrow injection but other 2 (33.33%) were not healed.

In14(70%)patients in a total 20 patients had nonunion in tibia. 12(85.71%) patients got union and 2 of them did not healed after bone marrow injections

Total of 20 patients, 12(60%) patient had closed fracture at the time of initial injury, 11(91.66%) patients got union and one patient did not achieve

union after bone marrow injections. From a total 20 patients 8(40%) patients had open fracture at the time of initial injury and 5(62.5%) patients of these 8 achieved union and 3 patients failed to achieve union after after marrow injection

Out of total 20 patients, union was achieved in 16 (80%) patients and 4 (20%) patients were fail to achieve union after bone marrow injections. One patient with nonunion got 3 injections and other 3 patients got 4 injections Overall results were excellent in 13 patients, good in three, fair in one, and poor in three patients. Union occurred in 16 patients. According to radiographic data the mean \pm SD healing time for healed patients was 85.875 \pm 2.927 days after bone marrow injections.

Discussion

In our study most of the patients had extensively scared skin. There are maximum chance of infection and wound problems after Open surgical procedures in these patients. The use of bone graft supplements like Amorphous Hydroxyapatite as an autogenous bone graft substitute has increased in nonunion. The bone graft acts as a scaffold with most of the cellular elements dying out and being replaced by creeping substitution²⁶.

Bone marrow consists of mesenchymal stem (marrow stromal cells) and various growth factors presnt in the plasma of natural medium . Multipotent stem cells are present in bone marrow These cell can be differentiate into many cells. Most common cells are Osteoblasts, Chondrocytes, Myocytes, Adipocytes, Beta pancreatic islets cells and Neuronal cells⁴.

Autocrine signals , Paracrine signals and Endocrine signals are known to be healing factors. Autocrine signals are generated by cells of same origin (a cell identical to signaling cell in phenotype). Paracrine signals are generated by cells of different phenotype and located close to first cell. Endocrine signals from cells of different phenotype and located in a remote site.

Growth factors have all these capacities. There are different kinds of growth factors. Each growth factor has a ligand receptor complex. The bone marrow contain both mesenchymal stem cells which are multipotent and growth factors. The bone marrow obtained by aspiration from the iliac

crest contained an average of 612 ± 134 progenitor cells/cm³ (range, 12 to 1224 progenitor cells/cm³)

. When a fracture is not united in an expected time without intervention it is called nonunion [6].

Standard bone grafting is much superior than bone marrow injection. But there also are many disadvantages of open bone grafting. The bone marrow injection has its own advantages.

There is less complication at donor and recipient sites. Bone marrow injection can be used at any area where skin condition is not suitable for open bone grafting and can be repeated easily.

Bone marrow contains osteogenic cells without devitalized tissue (dead bone) and most important it can be done in children.

Local anesthesia is needed as compared to general anesthesia. Bone marrow is safe and can be used even in a delayed union and finally it is practical and time saving and it is cost effective [7].

But it lacks providing immediate mechanical stability and has the risk of dilution with peripheral blood [7]. The mean age of the patients in our study was 37.667 years; it is similar to the Sim et al. [8], 38 years, and El Hussieny [9], 38 years, Connolly et al. [10] with 34 years, Arazi et al. [11], 34.3 years, Siwach et al. [12], 41.2 years, and 42 years by Willkins [13]. T Muschler et al. [14] reported that age is influencing the number of the nucleated cells, but also influencing the osteoblastic progenitors harvested from bone marrow by aspiration [15]. We have 20 patients with 80% : 20% male-to-female ratio; and was close to the Connolly et al. [10] with 70% : 30%, Jean et al. [16] with 71.4% : 28.6%, and El Hussieny [9] with 74% : 26%, and is in contrast to 57.2% : 42.8% male-to-female ratio with Matsuda et al. [17], Sim et al. [8] who had 90% : 10%, and 56.1% : 43.9% male-to-female ratio in study by Willkins [6]. Our results reported that, of the patients (n=6) who were smokers, 3 (50%) got union and other 3 (50%) smokers failed to get union. Similar results were reported by Reynders [18] and Connolly [19] mentioned a highly significant relationship between smoking and persistence of nonunion. The technique used in this study was similar to the technique described by Connolly et al. [19], Sebecic et al. [20], and

Siwach et al. [12], in respect to percutaneous aspiration of the marrow and its simultaneous injection in the nonunion site under fluoroscopic control.

5. Conclusion

Bone marrow injection is a natural form is effective and simple method without the disadvantages and complications of standard bone grafting and can be performed in poor skin condition with a scope for research in futures to how exactly healing is taking place in different situations.

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